

A Comparative Study On Effectiveness Of Integrated Management Versus Pharmacological Management In Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

Harish¹, N. Bhavitha¹, G. Sruthi¹, M. Dayana¹, M. Afridi¹, D. Nagaswetha²

¹PharmD Intern, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupathi, Andhra Pradesh, India.

ABSTRACT

Background: A comparative study was conducted on effectiveness of integrated management (combination of both pharmacological and non-pharmacological management) group-A versus pharmacological management group-B in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD). This study is to evaluate the effect of pharmacological and non-pharmacological management on COPD exacerbation rates and hospitalization frequency and the cost effectiveness of pharmacological interventions in managing Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD). **Aims and Objectives:** The aim is to comparing the effectiveness of integrated management vs pharmacological management in “COPD”. To assess the effect of pharmacological and non-pharmacological management on COPD exacerbation rates and hospitalization frequency. To Evaluate the Impact of Combined Pharmacological and Non- Pharmacological Interventions on Quality of Life. To Evaluate the Cost effectiveness of Pharmacological Interventions in Managing COPD. To compare the safety and Tolerability of Pharmacological and Non-Pharmacological interventions in COPD. **Materials and Methods:** A Prospective Observational Study was Conducted for 6 months (i.e. from December 2024 to May 2025) in Department of Respiratory Medicine at Sri Balaji Medical College Hospital and Research Institution Renigunta, Tirupati. Total of 90 Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease patients were recruited into the study based on the inclusion criteria upon receive of ICF. we will be categorised into Two Groups. To Group-A we gave only pharmacological treatment and to Group-B we gave integrated therapy (Both pharmacological and non-pharmacological). We used St. George’s Respiratory Questionnaire (SGRQ). **Results:** The study revealed that Pulmonary rehabilitation surpasses pharmacological treatment in enhancing patients' quality of life, particularly for chronic respiratory conditions like COPD. The majority of the patients are between age above 65 years (36%) and subjects 35 (50%) are smokers. And based on severity scale patients are mostly under the grade 2 Mmrc (64%), And we observed the subjects with FeV1 Ratio about (41%) in this study. **Conclusion:** This study concludes that Integrated therapy (pharmacological along with non-pharmacological treatment) in patients with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease improve the patient quality of life by relieving symptoms more than using only Pharmacological Treatment. And Pulmonary rehabilitation surpasses pharmacological treatment in enhancing patients' quality of life, particularly for chronic respiratory conditions like COPD.

Keywords: COPD, Integrated therapy, Pulmonary rehabilitation, Pharmacological management, SGRQ.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is a common, preventable, and treatable condition marked by persistent, usually progressive airflow limitation. It is primarily caused by an enhanced chronic inflammatory response in the lungs and airways to

harmful particles or gases, such as those found in cigarette smoke or environmental pollutants. This inflammation leads to narrowing of the airways and damage to lung tissue. Exacerbations sudden worsening of symptoms and the presence of other medical conditions (comorbidities) significantly contribute to the overall severity and impact of the

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disease on an individual's health, quality of life, and long-term prognosis. Early diagnosis and management are crucial.

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is a preventable and treatable respiratory condition primarily caused by smoking and long-term exposure to harmful chemical irritants. It is characterized by progressive and partially reversible airflow obstruction, along with lung hyperinflation. In addition to affecting the lungs, COPD has significant systemic effects and is often associated with a range of comorbid conditions, all of which can influence the overall severity and impact of the disease in individual patients.

COPD is a preventable and treatable disease that can cause significant systemic effects, complications, and comorbidities. Diagnosis is based on respiratory symptoms, a history of risk factor exposure, and confirmed airflow obstruction through spirometry. The WHO's GARD initiative emphasizes its preventable and manageable nature with appropriate care.

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is of growing concern due to its rising incidence. Contributing factors include the increasing life expectancy of the global population and the continued prevalence of smoking. Based on current trends, COPD was projected to become the third leading cause of death worldwide by 2020. This highlights the urgent need for greater awareness, prevention, and effective management of respiratory diseases globally.

ETIOLOGY: 1) Pollution 2) Chemical Exposure 3) Smoking 4) Chronic Bronchitis 5) Age

6) Genetic Predisposition 7) Epigenetic Factors 8) Irritants.

SYMPTOMS: 1) Dyspnoea 2) Chronic cough 3) Wheezing 4) Chest tightness 5) General fatigue 6) Shortness of breath 7) Episodes of worsening symptoms 8) Increased heart rate 9) Unintentional weight loss 10) Inflammation of the bronchial tubes 11) Loss of appetite 12) Decrease in muscle mass.

STAGES:

The stages of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) follow the guidelines established by the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD)

Stage 1: Mild COPD (Early Stage)

1. FEV1/FVC ratio: $\geq 80\%$ of the predicted value 2. Symptoms: Mild cough and occasional shortness of breath 3. Treatment: Smoking cessation, vaccinations, and bronchodilators as necessary

Stage 2: Moderate COPD 1. FEV1/FVC ratio: 50-79% of the predicted value 2. Symptoms: Persistent cough, shortness of breath, and wheezing 3. Treatment: Bronchodilators, combination therapy (such as inhalers), and pulmonary rehabilitation

Stage 3: Severe COPD

1. FEV1/FVC ratio: 30-49% of the predicted value 2. Symptoms: Notable shortness of breath, wheezing, and chronic cough 3. Treatment: Combination therapy, oral corticosteroids, and oxygen therapy if hypoxemic

Stage 4: Very Severe COPD

1. FEV1/FVC ratio: $< 30\%$ of the predicted value 2. Symptoms: Intense shortness of breath, wheezing, chronic cough, and frequent exacerbations 3. Treatment: Combination therapy, oxygen therapy, pulmonary rehabilitation, and consideration for lung transplantation

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

It is a Prospective Observational study and was conducted in departments of Sri Balaji medical care hospital (SBMHC), Renigunta, Tirupati The study was carried out for a period of 6 months from November 2024 to May 2025.

Study Design: Prospective observational study

Study Location: This study was conducted in the department of Respiratory Medicine at Sri

Balaji Medical College, Hospital & Research Institution Renigunta, Tirupati.

Study Duration: November 2024 to April 2025

Sample size: 90 patients.

Taking 6% as COPD prevalence in India

$$N = 4Pq/d^2$$

Sample size calculation: In our study 90 samples were recruited. The purpose of the study

was explained and written informed consent was obtained from all the participants.

Statistical analysis: All data will be entered and saved to Excel Software of Microsoft windows 2021. Baseline demographic clinical and laboratory data We summarised in the form of mean \pm standard deviation (SD) or median for continuous variables.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Individuals Aged >45Years.
- Diagnosis of COPD confirmed by spirometry.
- Both males and females.
- Stable COPD (no exacerbations within 4 weeks)

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Severe comorbidities (heart failure, cancer, pulmonary embolism or stroke)
- Severe cognitive impairment or dementia Patients.
- Patient who are not willing to Perform.
- Patients with O₂'[oxygen] dependence like Ambulatory Issue.

STUDY MATERIALS:

1. Patient Informed Consent Form.
2. Patient Data Collection Proforma.

3. St. George's Respiratory Questionnaire. (SGRQ)

1.Patient informed consent form: It is of the utmost importance that the human volunteer participating in a scientific research project, for instance a clinical study, understanding all details of the planned experiment on basis of these regulations, an informed consent document was prepared for this study and properly used.

2.Patient data collection proforma: Standard form was prepared by using various literatures to collect all the necessary data from the study subjects. Data includes patient demographic details, past medical history, medication history, life style and personal habits of patients.

3.ST. GEORGE'S RESPIRATORY QUESTIONNAIRE: This questionnaire is designed to help us learn much more about how your breathing is troubling you and how it affects your life. This method consists of 50 questions yes/no type questions and 1 point is assigned for each positive response and it is documented and then the score is interpreted for mild, moderate, severe, very severe. To measure health impairment in patients with COPD.

RESULTS:

A Prospective Observational Study was Conducted for 6 months (i.e. from November 2024 to April 2025) in Department of Respiratory Medicine at **Sri Balaji Medical College Hospital and Research Institution** Renigunta, Tirupati. A Total of 90 Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease patients were recruited into the study based on the inclusion criteria upon receive of ICF.

A Total of 90 Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Patients were recruited in our Study and we will be categorised into Two Groups. To Group-A we gave only pharmacological treatment and to Group-B we gave integrated therapy (Both pharmacological and non-pharmacological).

Gender: Out of 90 subjects 18 were female population and 72 were male population.

AGE: We categorised the patients of their age groups. Out of 90 patients were under the age groups

of 45-55 years were (15), followed by 55-65 years (32), followed by 65-75 years (23) followed by 75-85 years (15) followed by 85 -95 years (5).

Table no 1: Shows distribution of subjects based on their age group

S. No	Age group (In years)	Male	Female	No of Subjects	Percentage (%)
1	46-55	10	5	15	17
2	56-65	29	3	32	36
3	66-75	22	1	23	26
4	76-85	10	5	15	17
5	86-95	3	2	5	4
	Total	74	16	90	100
Mean	14.8	3.2	18		
Standard Deviation	9.37	1.79	10.1		

Personal Habits: We have assessed the personal habits of study subjects and found that were having personal habits, 35(50%) subjects were smokers, 20(25%) subjects were alcoholic, 17(25%) subjects were both alcoholics and smokers.

Table no. 2: Shows distribution of subjects based on their personal habits

S. No	Habits	No. Of Subjects (N=90)	Percentage (%)
1	Alcoholic	20	18%
2	Smoker	35	31.5%
3	Both Smoker alcoholic	17	15.3%
	Total	72	64.8%

Severity:

We categorised the subjects based on their severity. Out of 90 Subjects 46 (41.4%) were diagnosed with

grade 2 followed by 20 subjects (18%) were diagnosed with grade 1 followed by 8 subjects (7.2%) were diagnosed with grade 3 followed by 6 subjects ((5.4%) were diagnosed with grade 1 respectively.

Table no.3: Shows distribution of subjects based on their severity

S. No	Grade	Severity	No. of Subjects	Percentage (%)
1	Grade-1	Mild	20	18%
2	Grade-2	Moderate	46	41.4%
3	Grade-3	Moderately-Severe	8	7.2%
4	Grade-4	Severe	6	5.4%

FEV1 & FVC RATIO:

Out of 90 Subjects 35 (41%) of subjects have ratio between 70- 75, followed by 20 (23%) of subjects

have ratio between 65-70, followed by 25(21%) of subjects have ratio of 60-65, followed by 10 (15%) of subject's ratio between 55-60 and 0(0%) subjects are in the ratio of <60.

Table no.4: Shows distribution of subjects based on FeV1 & FvC

S. NO	Ratio of FEV1 & FVC	No. of Subjects (n= 90)	Percentage (%)
1	<60	0	0
2	70 - 75	35	31.5%
3	65 - 70	20	18%
4	60 – 65	25	22.5%
5	55 -60	10	9%
	Total	90	100%

DRUG THERAPY:

Out of 90 Subjects 45 subjects (50%) were taken pharmacological treatment followed by 45 subjects

(50%) were taken both pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatment.

Table no.5: Shows distribution of subjects based on drug therapy

S.no	Type of drug therapy	No of subjects	Percentage (%)
1	Pharmacological	45	50%
2	Pharmacological & Pulmonary Rehabilitation	45	50%
	Total	90	100%

PHARMACOLOGICAL MANGEMENT:

Out of 90 subjects the pharmacological management were given to 45 subjects in that 32

(54%) subjects were reduced the symptoms; disease progression was reduced among them 13(19%) of subject doesn't show the more effectiveness on their subjects.

reduced among them 5(11%) of subject doesn't show the more effectiveness on their subjects.

St. George's Respiratory Questionnaire:(SGRQ)

The St. George's Respiratory Questionnaire (SGRQ) is designed to measure health impairment in patients with COPD.

Four scores are calculated:

INTEGRATED MANAGEMENT

Out of 90 subjects the integrated management were given to 45 subjects in that 40 (89%) subjects were reduced the symptoms; disease progression was

1. Symptoms
2. Activity
3. Impacts

4. Total

According to Score:

50 (Very Severe Impairment)

40 (Severe Impairment)

30 (Very Moderate Impairment)

20 (Moderate Impairment)

10 (Mild Impairment)

Table no.6: Shows St. George's Respiratory Questionnaire score

S NO	SCORE	INITIAL	FINAL
1	50	43	31
2	40	32	24
3	30	23	19
4	20	14	11
5	10	06	04

DISCUSSION

In our research, we found that Integrated therapy, which includes both pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatments, enhances the quality of life for patients with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) by alleviating symptoms more effectively than pharmacological treatment alone, as noted by **Anees Ur Rehman et al.** We divided the patients based on their Drug Therapy into two distinct groups. The first group is referred to as pharmacological therapy, which comprises 50% of the population, while the second group is identified as integrated therapy (combining pharmacological and non-pharmacological approaches), also encompassing 50% of the population. Additionally, we classified the patients according to their age. The average age of the entire study is between 45 and 55 years. The male population totals 74, while the female population consists of 16 individuals. We aimed to investigate the influence of smoking habits on Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease and found that 49% of the patients with a smoking history are more susceptible to COPD.

Another critical factor in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease is age. We evaluated the

population aged 55 to 65 years, which constitutes 34% of those more prone to COPD. Personal habits significantly contribute to the onset of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease. Our assessment of personal habits revealed that smokers represent a substantial 49%. A notable characteristic of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease is dyspnoea. We utilized the mMRC Dyspnoea grade to measure the severity of breathlessness and discovered that 64% of subjects fell into Grade II. According to the St. George's Respiratory Questionnaire, the average initial score was 17.8, while the final score was 23.6, indicating a marked improvement in the patients' condition, suggesting a reduction or normalization of symptoms. Furthermore, in this study, we examined the management strategy where 40 out of 90 subjects received a combination of Pharmacological and Non-Pharmacological interventions. This group demonstrated significant enhancements in various health metrics, which included lung function, muscle strength, decreased disease severity, and an overall improvement in quality of life. Based on this evidence, we establish that an integrated management approach is likely to produce superior outcomes in the treatment of COPD, thereby enhancing patients' quality of life.

CONCLUSION

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is one of the most common respiratory ailments, posing a significant challenge as it diminishes the quality of life for those affected. This research was conducted to investigate how pulmonary rehabilitation outperforms pharmacological treatments in improving the quality of life for patients, particularly those suffering from chronic respiratory diseases such as COPD. Our study's findings led us to conclude that an integrated approach, combining pharmacological interventions with pulmonary rehabilitation, significantly enhances the condition of patients, especially in the case of COPD. Ultimately, this research indicates that pulmonary rehabilitation is a groundbreaking approach for managing chronic respiratory illnesses, particularly chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Moreover, the findings of this study contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the role of pulmonary rehabilitation as a vital component in the management of chronic respiratory

diseases. As healthcare systems continue to evolve, it is crucial to prioritize strategies that enhance patient outcomes and quality of life. The implications of this research extend beyond COPD, as the principles of pulmonary rehabilitation can be applied to various chronic respiratory conditions, thereby improving the overall standard of care.

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